

ESSENTIAL OILS OF SOME OPEN SEEDED PLANTS

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Abstract: *Pinus brutia* var. *eldarica* (Medw.) Silba, *Juniperus seravschanica* Kom., *Juniperus virginiana* L., *Thuja occidentalis* L., *Cupressus sempervirens* f. *horizontalis* (Mill.) Voss, essential oils were extracted from their green branches and leaves of Eldar pine using the Ginzberg method [1].

Key words: essential oil plants, essential oils, Ginzberg method.

Material and methods: As the material and object of the work, 5 representatives of the class of pines growing and cultivated in Surkhandarya region were selected: *Pinus brutia* var. *eldarica* (Medw.) Silba, *Juniperus seravschanica* Kom. [2-3]), *Juniperus virginiana* L., *Thuja occidentalis* L., *Cupressus sempervirens* f. *horizontalis* (Mill.) Voss, their green branches and leaves of Eldar pine Ginzberg essential oils were extracted using the method.

Pinus brutia var. *eldarica* (Medw.) Silba (homeland of Azerbaijan), *Cupressus sempervirens* f. *horizontalis* (Mill.) Voss (Mediterranean), *Juniperus virginiana* L. and *Thuja occidentalis* L. of North American origin are planted as ornamental plants in Surkhandarya region [4]. *Juniperus seravschanica* Kom. is found in the mountainous regions of Uzbekistan and forms thick forests in some places. *Juniperus seravschanica* Kom. has a unique aroma and is used as a spice in cooking various meat products. Because a large amount of essential oils are collected in its branches and domes [5]. All of the plants listed above are plants rich in essential oils. In the plant, the places where essential oils accumulate surrounded by thick cells are located in the lower part of the parenchyma cells of the cuticle, epidermis, hypodermis of leaves and domes in the schizogen type [6]. Such a deep location of essential oil collection sites requires long boiling or shearing and grinding to extract them [7].

Therefore, in order to determine the periods of maximum release of essential oils in plant organs, we used boiling schemes every 8, 12, 14 and 16 hours.

The amount of essential oils extracted from plant organs is presented in the table. As can be seen from the data in the table, the places where essential oils accumulate in the organs of these plants are endogenous organs, and in particular, they are of the schizogen type.

Almost 51-58% of the available essential oils are released when the green branches of *J. seravschanica* and *J. virginiana* and *C. sempervirens* are boiled for 8-9 hours. As the time of boiling the plant product increased, the amount of extracted essential oils also increased, and almost 2 times more essential oils were extracted from the plant organs boiled for 14 hours. Boiling longer than this period (in the case of *J. seravschanica*) did not significantly affect the separation of essential oils.

Thus, it is enough to boil the products for 14 hours to extract essential oils from the stems and leaves of the experimental plants.

Judging from the data in the table, among these plants, the plant with the richest essential oils is *J. seravschanica*. In its green branches, up to 1.35% of essential oils are collected by wet weight. As a result of the experiment, it was found that the branches of *J. virginiana* and *C. sempervirens* also secrete a significant amount of essential oils (up to 0.61-0.46%). The content of essential oils was found to be slightly lower (0.12 %) in western camellia twigs, and much lower (0.05 %) in Eldar pine leaves.

Table.

Amount of essential oils extracted from plant organs (in % of wet weight).

T/ p	Plant type	Organ	Boiling time, hours			
			8	12	14	16
			Amount of essential oil, %			
1.	<i>Juniperus zeravschanica</i> Kom.	A green branch	0.7	0.82	1.35	1.32
2.	<i>J. virginiana</i> L.	A green branch	0.35	0.60	0.61	-
3.	<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i> L.	A green branch	0.30	0.45	0.46	-
4.	<i>Thuya occidentalis</i> L.	A green branch	0.10	0.12	0.12	-
5.	<i>Pinus eldarica</i> (Medw.) Silba	Leaf	Traces of essential oil	0.04	0.05	-

The extracted essential oils are pale yellow in color and have an aromatic smell. Essential oils of the above types can be used for various purposes. In the future, it is aimed to study the amount of essential oils collected in plants of different sexes and their vegetative and generative organs, as well as the chemical composition and pharmacological properties of the extracted essential oils.

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